

SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pARTicle Data (SPEARHEAD)

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JupyterHub for SPEARHEAD Tools

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List of Acronyms

D	Deliverable
ESA	European Space Agency
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
LDAP	Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
OAuth	Open Authorization
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SQ	Science Question
TLJH	The Littlest JupyterHub
TO	Technical Objective
VDA	Velocity dispersion analysis
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a report on the *JupyterHub for SPEARHEAD Tools*. First, a short general introduction is given about what a JupyterHub is, followed by an overview of the specific setup of the project's JupyterHub system. Furthermore, it is described how users interact with the system and how it enables them to access selected Python tools provided by the [SPEARHEAD](#) project without requiring a local Python installation.

1 Introduction

The **SPEARHEAD** project aims to answer three main Science Questions (**SQs**):

- **SQ1: How are ions and electrons accelerated to the highest energies in solar eruptions, beyond 100 MeV/n and 1 MeV, respectively?**
- **SQ2: What are the processes governing particle release** from acceleration sites in the solar corona?
- **SQ3: What are the key processes of high-energy particle transport** in the interplanetary medium, in the magnetosphere and in the atmosphere?

In order to achieve these goals, three main Technical Objectives (**TOs**) of the project are proposed:

- **TO1: to develop and distribute analysis tools** to extract high-energy particle fluxes from particle detectors designed to operate at lower energies or to yield monitoring data. Response functions of spacecraft instruments will be determined and particle fluxes of the very high energy particles as a function of time and energy will be delivered.
- **TO2: to process and cross-calibrate a large number of data to produce high-energy particle flux datasets** and distribute them to the community.
- **TO3: to validate the data against intermittent direct spectrometer observations.**

As part of achieving **TO1** and in support of addressing the **SQs**, the project is actively and continuously developing a suite of software tools. These tools are designed not only to support internal project goals, but also to benefit the wider scientific community. To ensure broad accessibility and encourage collaboration, the tools are openly shared via the project's GitHub repositories, as documented in Deliverable (D) 6.2 (Gieseler et al. 2024).

Building on this effort, the project is also deploying a dedicated JupyterHub environment for the **SPEARHEAD** tools, which is described in this document. This cloud-based platform significantly enhances the usability and outreach potential of selected tools developed within the project. By providing a ready-to-use, browser-accessible interface with all necessary dependencies pre-installed, JupyterHub removes the need for users to install software locally. This lowers the entry barrier for new users, fosters reproducible research, and accelerates the adoption of **SPEARHEAD** tools by researchers and stakeholders across disciplines.

2 JupyterHub for **SPEARHEAD** tools

2.1 General information about JupyterHub

JupyterHub is an open-source, multi-user platform designed to provide access to interactive computing environments through a standard web browser. In the context of the server infrastructure of the **SPEARHEAD** project, JupyterHub serves as a central access point, enabling users to interact with shared computational resources and project-specific tools in a secure, scalable, and user-friendly manner.

Designed to support multiple users on a single machine or across a distributed cluster, JupyterHub allows each participant to independently launch and manage their own Jupyter Notebook sessions. These environments can be pre-configured with all necessary dependencies, including scientific libraries, data processing tools, and domain-specific software packages aligned with the project's research objectives. This eliminates the need for individual users to install or configure software locally, thereby reducing technical barriers and promoting consistent, reproducible workflows.

JupyterHub

All icons were obtained on Flaticon (<https://www.flaticon.com/packs/essential-collection>)

Figure 1: Schematic illustrating an example JupyterHub system (obtained from <https://jupyterhub.readthedocs.io>, May 2025)

To ensure secure and compliant access, JupyterHub integrates seamlessly with various authentication systems (e.g., Open Authorization (OAuth), Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP), or institutional single sign-on), ensuring controlled access and compliance with data governance standards. Figure 1 shows an example JupyterHub system behind an Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) proxy that utilizes custom server configurations, authenticators¹ as described above, and custom Spawners² that can run scripts before the user's server creation. This flexible architecture ensures robust session management and supports dynamic resource allocation according to user and project needs.

2.2 Setup used in SPEARHEAD

To address the specific needs of the consortium while maintaining a lightweight and maintainable setup, SPEARHEAD makes use of a streamlined distribution of JupyterHub known as The Littlest JupyterHub (TLJH). TLJH is particularly well-suited for smaller teams or single-server deployments, making it ideal for hosting project-specific tools and datasets in a centralized and easily accessible location. Despite its simplified architecture, TLJH retains and thus provides many of the core features of JupyterHub, including individual user environments, pre-configured access to Jupyter Notebooks, and customizable computing environments with domain-specific libraries and tools. TLJH also simplifies installation and system administration by bundling key components into a server-ready package, thereby significantly reducing the operational overhead compared to more complex JupyterHub setups.

¹<https://jupyterhub.readthedocs.io/en/stable/reference/authenticators.html>

²<https://jupyterhub.readthedocs.io/en/stable/reference/api/spawner.html>

Within the **SPEARHEAD** context, **TLJH** is deployed on a virtual server managed by National Observatory of Athens (**NOA**), and provides a common interface for data exploration, visualization, and processing. This deployment includes role-based access control, ensuring that only authorized users can access project resources. As detailed in D6.2, the **SPEARHEAD** GitHub organization at <https://github.com/spearhead-he> hosts the individual repositories of the project's tools. Two of them, **bowtie**³ and Velocity dispersion analysis (**VDA**)⁴, are provided as Jupyter Notebooks, making them executable within the JupyterHub environment. To ensure that users always have access to the most up-to-date versions of these tools, the project has implemented an automated synchronization pipeline. Therefore, the latest versions of the tools as they are provided through the GitHub repositories are automatically cloned to the JupyterHub. For this, a combination of a third party library called `nbgitpuller`⁵ and a custom Spawner are utilized to ensure the best user experience. `nbgitpuller` enables seamless distribution of content to JupyterHub users through the use of clickable links. This approach allows users to access and update materials without requiring any knowledge of git or version control systems, streamlining the user experience and reducing technical barriers. In case of conflicts between GitHub repository and JupyterHub files, `nbgitpuller` by default would choose the JupyterHub version over the repository's. This practically means that whenever there are updates in the **SPEARHEAD** tools' GitHub repositories, while the user also has changed files such as the Jupyter Notebooks on the JupyterHub, files might not get fetched properly. To solve this problem, custom Spawners are used. A Spawner is a Python module and class included in JupyterHub that starts each single-user notebook server⁶. As JupyterHub supports multiple users, an instance of the Spawner subclass is created for each user. For example, if there are 20 active JupyterHub users, there will be 20 instances of the subclass at the same time. Spawners have the ability to define custom Python scripts or functions that will run in various stages of the server's creation. The custom functions defined for **SPEARHEAD**'s JupyterHub server are (a) the `pre_spawn_hook` and (b) the `post_stop_hook`. The former allows bootstrapping work before the Spawner starts and is specifically used to create backups for the user's cloned repositories. The latter is executed after the server has stopped non-forcefully. In **SPEARHEAD**'s case, it checks if the newly pulled files are identical to the backups created by the `pre_spawn_hook`, and if so, deletes the backup files. By utilizing the above methods, the user:

- does not need to worry about losing the latest changes
- does not have to know about the underlying git fetches
- always sees the latest version of the **SPEARHEAD** tools
- does not lose their changes after a fetch
- does not have to restart their JupyterHub server to update files from GitHub

The entire synchronization and conflict-resolution process, through the use of `nbgitpuller` and the custom Spawner, is invisible to users, aside from a short loading period when the server starts. This behavior is illustrated in Fig. 3. Therefore, by integrating `nbgitpuller` with customized Spawner logic, **SPEARHEAD** ensures a robust, low-barrier, and user-centric environment for collaborative scientific computing — helping researchers focus on data analysis and tool application rather than software maintenance or system administration.

³<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14505387>

⁴<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14441054>

⁵<https://nbgitpuller.readthedocs.io>

⁶A single-user notebook server is the environment dedicated to a single user. There, the user can add or delete files and run executables. Users cannot interact with the dedicated servers of each other.

2.3 User engagement

To access the **SPEARHEAD** tools on the project’s JupyterHub server, users begin by navigating to the project’s official website <https://spearhead-he.eu>. Under the "Results" section, they can select (click on) the “Tools” button as shown in Fig. 2. There, all the developed tools are listed along with the respective individual links to the JupyterHub. Each link is different and dedicated to the described tool. By opening (clicking on) one of these links, the user is redirected to the **SPEARHEAD** JupyterHub server. After a short (few seconds) initialization period, the system spawns a single-user server (Fig. 3) and automatically loads the main notebook associated with the selected tool (Fig. 4). From there, users can interact with the Jupyter Notebook in their browser exactly as they would in a local environment — executing code cells, visualizing data, and modifying content in real time.

Figure 2: How a user can navigate to the **SPEARHEAD** JupyterHub. (1) Visit the **SPEARHEAD** website, (2) Click on "Results" in the top navigation panel, (3) Click on the "Tools" icon, (4) Click on the "Use the tool in JupyterHub" link of the wanted tool.

The JupyterHub interface also allows users to browse and manage files within their personal workspace, accessible via the left-hand sidebar. Since each user operates within a private home directory on the

server, any changes they make — whether editing notebooks or creating new files — remain isolated and do not affect the original tool code or other users’ environments. In case the user wants to open another SPEARHEAD tool, they have to access it by clicking on its respective link on the project’s website so that it will be updated properly by nbgitpuller.

In the upper right of the JupyterHub interface (Fig. 4), the user can optionally change the Python environment (called kernel) in which the opened notebook is executed. This functionality should usually not be needed because the entire system is set up so that the correct Python environment (provided by conda⁷) is selected for each respective tool. These environments are specifically configured so that they contain all required packages and the user does not need to think about any installations or dependencies.

Figure 3: The loading states before the JupyterHub single-user server environment is shown to the user. First, checks are made and backups are created (top image). Afterwards, the latest version of the tool is copied from the corresponding GitHub repository (bottom).

Figure 4: Jupyter Notebook of the bowtie tool opened on the SPEARHEAD JupyterHub.

All Python-based tools provided via the SPEARHEAD GitHub organization and deployed on the

⁷<https://conda.org>

SPEARHEAD JupyterHub server have been tested for usability and robustness. Notably, in May 2025, the tools and the platform were successfully used by students and researchers during the SPEARHEAD MSc course focusing on *High Energy Particles* at the University of Turku (<https://spearhead-he.eu/msc-course/>). The participants, who had not been involved in the project development, provided hands-on feedback that contributed to further refinements. Additionally, at the SPEARHEAD Workshop 2 in June 2025 (<https://spearhead-he.eu/workshop-2/>), selected tools and their JupyterHub-based implementations were demonstrated, tested, and discussed in depth with workshop participants, members of the External Advisory Committee⁸ attending the workshop, and domain experts. These sessions validated the usability of the infrastructure in real-world settings and confirmed its value as a scientific dissemination and collaboration platform.

3 Conclusions and outlook

The deployment of JupyterHub, and specifically its lightweight variant, The Littlest JupyterHub (TLJH), within the SPEARHEAD infrastructure provides a reliable, accessible, and user-friendly environment for hosting the project's tools. This setup streamlines user interaction by automating repository management, ensuring correct environment setup, and integrating role-based access control. As a result, users can fully concentrate on the scientific content without needing to manage technical aspects and complex configurations. The infrastructure is designed to support both internal project partners and external users, playing a key role in enabling reproducible analysis, collaborative development, and efficient dissemination of results across the consortium and the wider scientific community.

In parallel, SPEARHEAD has gained early developer access to ESA Datalabs⁹, a cloud-based computing environment developed by the European Space Agency (ESA), which offers functionality similar to a JupyterHub system and also supports Jupyter Notebooks. As part of Work Package (WP) 6, selected SPEARHEAD tools have already been successfully adapted and deployed within the ESA Datalabs environment. This parallel deployment not only enhances the tools' accessibility, but also ensures their long-term availability and scientific impact, extending their reach beyond the lifetime of the SPEARHEAD project through integration with an established European infrastructure.

⁸<https://spearhead-he.eu/external-advisory-committee/>

⁹<https://datalabs.esa.int>

Bibliography

Gieseler, J., Vasalos, G., Köberle, M., et al. 2024, Deliverable 6.2: SPEARHEAD GitHub repository, Report, SPEARHEAD Project